

Call center data modeling: a queueing science approach based on Markovian arrival processes

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Abstract

In this paper we analyze the well-known “Anonymous bank” call center dataset from a queueing science viewpoint. For this purpose, fitted distributions for both the inter-arrival and service times as well as for customers patiences are integrated in a simulator to infer quantities of interest related to call centers managerial decisions as waiting times, abandonment rates and queue lengths. In particular, it is shown how a type of Markov renewal process, the Markovian arrival process (*MAP*), is able to capture some of the characterizing properties of arrivals in a modern call center as overdispersion and positive correlation between arrival counts. The work provides a new inference approach for the *MAP* based on the count process descriptors and presents new properties concerning the dependence structure of the cumulated number of arrivals in a *MAP*.

Key words: Call center; Markovian arrival process; Lognormal distribution; Overdispersion; Impatient customers; Queueing Science.

1 Introduction

Telephone call centers have become a crucial element in most large companies as financial entities, insurance companies or healthcare institutions, among others. In the era of big data, call center managers are aware that high efficiency and profitability depend on a correct stochastic modeling based on recorded datasets. Thus, in the latest decades different authors have studied the empirical behavior of modern call center data, see for example Gans et al. [2003], Avramidis et al. [2004], Brown et al. [2005], Aksin et al.

[2007], Jouini et al. [2013]. In particular, Avramidis et al. [2004] establishes the main characterizing properties of modern call centers data, namely:

- P1. *The total daily demand (number of calls) shows overdispersion relative to the Poisson distribution (the variance is greater than the mean).*
- P2. *The arrival rate varies considerably with the time of day.*
- P3. *There is a strong positive correlation between arrival counts in a time partition of a day.*
- P4. *There is significant dependency between arrivals counts on successive days.*

The term *Queueing science* has been adopted in the recent queueing literature to denote data-driven mathematical models aimed to reproduce and predict the observed queueing systems data behaviour. A number of papers have contributed in this research area lately, see Brown et al. [2005], Soyer and Tarimcilar [2008], Demiriz et al. [2009], Aktekin and Soyer [2012], Ibrahim and L'Ecuyer [2013], Ding et al. [2015], Armony et al. [2015], Barrow and Kourentzes [2018], Azriel et al. [2019], Hathaway et al. [2021], Albrecht et al. [2021]. This paper also undertakes a *Queueing science* perspective since it deals with exploratory analysis, statistical modeling and performance estimation of the queueing system generated by the well known "Anonymous bank" call center data (already analyzed by some of the previous references). Specifically, from the empirical properties of the dataset we propose a multi-server queueing model that is fitted using tools from statistical inference, mathematical optimization and simulation. The arrival process of the considered queue is governed by a Markovian arrival process (*MAP*), a type of Markovian renewal process that allows for overdispersion and positively correlated arrival counts, see Neuts [1979], Lucantoni [1991a], Asmussen and Koole [1993], Chakravarty [2001]. The services times are fitted by a Lognormal (*LN*) distribution and customers impatience times are modeled by a Birnbaum-Saunders (*BS*) distribution.

While estimation of the service and impatience times is straightforward, statistical inference for the arrival *MAP* process requires more effort, specially if some of the previous P1-P4 counting process properties are to be captured. Most of papers dealing with estimation for different classes of *MAP*s have relied on the properties of the inter-arrival times distribution and, based on this, different inference paradigms as the moment matching method, EM algorithm or Bayesian strategies have been considered. See for example, Bodrog et al. [2008], Scott and Smyth [2003], Casale et al. [2010], Rodríguez et al. [2015], Yera et al. [2019], Breuer [2002], Okamura and Dohi [2016], Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2017, 2021]. However, less approaches have considered the inclusion of the counting process properties in the estimation method [Eum et al., 2007, Nasr et al., 2018, Okamura et al., 2009, Breuer and Kume, 2010] which, as will be illustrated in this paper, is highly advisable for an accurate capture of the characterizing call center data properties.

The *MAP* is a particular case of the batch Markovian arrival process (*BMAP*) who shares the same definition and properties as the *MAP* but which also allows for arrivals in batches. The literature on queues where either a *MAP* or *BMAP* governs the arrival process is vast. A detailed theoretical analysis of the *MAP/G/1* queue was first considered by Ramaswami [1980]. In Lucantoni et al. [1990], Lucantoni [1991b, 1993], an exhaustive analysis of the *BMAP/G/1* is provided and closed-form expressions for the transforms and generating functions of the stationary and transient distributions for the queue length and waiting time distributions are given. Since then, many works considering extensions or specific cases of such seminal works have been proposed. For example, Chaudhry et al. [2013], Gupta et al. [2016], Singh et al. [2016], Pradhan and Gupta [2019, 2022], Dudin et al. [2023], Liu and Li [2024], propose incorporating the *MAP* as input to a one-server system. Queues with input flow described by either a *MAP* or *BMAP* with more than one server have been analyzed by Breuer [2001], Choi et al. [2004], Wu et al. [2011], Kim et al. [2017], Klimenok and Dudina [2017], Kawanishi and Takine [2016]. In addition, Kawanishi and Takine [2016] incorporates impatience times when addressing the analysis of the systems *MAP/M/c* and *M/PH/c*. Impatience has been also considered by Choi et al. [2004], Chakravarthy [2009], Gursoy et al. [2022]. Some versions considering retrial in *MAP*-based queueing systems are Kim and Kim [2010], Wu et al. [2011], Dudina et al. [2013]. Finally, priority has been also incorporated in the analysis of *MAP*-based queues as it is the case of Takine [1999], Xue and Alfa [2011]. For a complete review of applications of *MAPs* in queueing theory, we refer the reader to Chapter 4 of He [2014].

Most of approximations to *MAP*-based queueing systems have been adopted from either a theoretical viewpoint or a numerical one, this last focused on the inversion of transforms and approximation of performance measures. Many of these papers present simulation studies, where the quantities of interest are computed assuming fixed generator parameters but in most works, the quantities of interest associated with the queue are given through equations from which it is difficult to extract practical information. Less approaches have been, however, devoted to data-driven queueing system. See for example, Klemm et al. [2003], Okamura et al. [2009] which assume a deterministic service time distribution and Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2017], where exponential service times are considered. Up to our knowledge, the queueing system *MAP/LN/C* with impatient customers considered in this paper has not been analyzed before.

The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows. First, from a queueing science point of view and motivated by the “Anonymous bank” dataset, we propose a data-driven queueing model that captures some of the observed empirical properties. By separately fitting the arrival, service and impatience times, we propose a simulator of the data queueing behavior that allows the user to estimate some quantities of interest for managerial decision makers as abandon rates, virtual waiting times and queue length distributions. The paper also presents novel methodological contributions regarding *MAPs*. On one hand, a novel optimization-based fitting approach for the *MAP₂* is proposed, where *MAP₂* denotes that a *MAP* with two states has been fitted. The method

takes as starting point two previous approaches to inference for MAP_2 s [Rodríguez et al., 2015, Ramírez-Cobo et al., 2021] which are adapted to integrate information regarding the counting process. On another hand, new theoretical properties concerning the covariance and correlation patterns of the counting process in a MAP are obtained. This properties are of interest for queueing scientists which, guided by their data properties, look for suitable stochastic models. Although this paper is focused on call center data, there are multiple contexts characterized by dependent inter-event times where the considered stochastic model can be useful for decision makers as reliability, teletraffic, electrical engineering or biostatistics. See for example Xu et al. [2024], Wang et al. [2023], Kang et al. [2002], Chen et al. [2021], Chang [2020], Vanberkel et al. [2018], Dudin et al. [2020].

This paper is organised as follows. The description of the “Anonymous bank” dataset along with an exploratory data analysis are considered in Section 2. Section 3, deals with known and novel properties of the arrival process, the MAP . Section 4, is devoted to the optimization-based new method for statistical inference for the MAP_2 . Section 5, presents the main contribution to queueing science of the paper which is the data-driven $MAP_2/LN/C$ model with impatience times as well as a simulator of the system to obtain performance measure of interest. Conclusions and possible extensions to this work are finally considered in Section 6.

2 “Anonymous bank” call center data

This work is motivated by the analysis of the so-called “Anonymous bank” Israeli call center data. This is a dataset publicly available at

<http://iew3.technion.ac.il/serveng/callcenterdata/index.html>

that contains detailed information concerning the calls produced over the period of 12 months from January 1999 until December 1999. This dataset has been extensively analyzed in previous *queueing science* studies, see for example Brown et al. [2005], Aktekin and Soyer [2012], Jouini et al. [2013]. The functioning of the call center is summarized next. A customer calls a telephone number depending on the type of required service and then she is connected to a VRU. Next, the customer performs either any kind of transaction or indicates the need to speak with an agent. According to Brown et al. [2005] around 35% of customers belong to this second category. If at this moment any agent is free then the customer is automatically connected with her, and thus the customer’s waiting time is equal to 0. Otherwise, the customer joins a queue. The time of arrival is understood as the time the customer exists the VRU (either for being directly serviced or for joining the queue). A portion of customers who enter the queue abandon before being served. For those who remain, their waiting times as well as their services times are recorded. Concerning the number of servers (C), according to the web site information there were 8 agent positions and 5 agent positions for internet services, but in our simulations (see

Section 5) we have not assumed a specific value and instead, we have compared results for an assortment of values of C . Additional information as the priority of the customer (high-priority or regular) or the type of service is also available although it has not been considered in our study.

Consider the times of arrivals. Our analysis was focused on the 44 weekdays (Sunday to Thursday) in November and December and only on *regular activity* (PS) calls in the same spirit as in many of the analyses in Brown et al. [2005]. The PS type of calls was the most numerous and a total of $n = 42616$ calls between November and December were registered. During the weekdays the call center was staffed from 7 am to midnight. The sample consists of 44 traces of inter-arrival times (in hours), $\mathbf{t}^{(i)} = (t_1^{(i)}, \dots, t_{n_i}^{(i)})$, where $i = 1, \dots, 44$ represents the day, n_i is the number of calls occurred at the i -th day and $n = \sum_{i=1}^{44} n_i$.

Figure 1 depicts the average number of calls per day, including weekdays and weekends. Clearly, the weekends (Fridays and Saturdays) present a different behavior and should be differently treated. Instead, all weekdays present a similar pattern and in this work days from Sundays to Thursday have been assumed as generated from the same stochastic process. From an applied viewpoint, this means that data from the weekdays were aggregated. As already stated by property P2 in Section 1, it is evident that the arrival rate varies with the time of the day.

Figure 1: Average number of calls per hour per day in data call center.

In order to fragment the weekdays into homogeneous slots, the Tuckey's test was

applied. As a result, six time slots (with accepted homogeneity within each slot) were set:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_1 &= 7 - 9 \text{ hours,} \\
 G_2 &= 9 - 11 \text{ hours,} \\
 G_3 &= 11 - 16 \text{ hours,} \\
 G_4 &= 16 - 17 \text{ hours,} \\
 G_5 &= 17 - 22 \text{ hours,} \\
 G_6 &= 22 - 24 \text{ hours.}
 \end{aligned}$$

An exponential distribution, the simplest model for inter-arrival times in the literature, was fitted to the times between the occurrence of consecutive calls. Figure 2 depicts the plot of the empirical quantiles versus those of the fitted exponential distribution for a random day of each time slot ($G_1 - G_3$ in the top panels, $G_4 - G_6$ in the bottom panels). As can be seen, the exponential distribution is not a proper model for the inter-arrival times, and therefore, the Poisson process neither is for modeling the counting process.

Figure 2: QQ-plots of times between calls: empirical versus exponential distribution. The top panels refers to time slots $G_1 - G_3$ and the bottom panels to $G_4 - G_6$.

The arrival times in the dataset also satisfy properties P1 and P3 stated in Section 1. In particular, overdispersion occurs when the variance of the counting process is larger than the mean. The classic measure for overdispersion is the Variance-to-Mean ratio (or Index of Dispersion of Counts), see Lindsey [1995], Andersen and Nielsen [2002]. Specifically, if $N(\tau)$ denotes the stationary number of arrivals in an interval of length τ ,

then the Variance-to-Mean ratio is defined as

$$VtM[N(\tau)] = \frac{V[N(\tau)]}{E[N(\tau)]}. \quad (2.1)$$

The larger the value of (2.1) is, the more deviated from the Poisson process data are. In the case of the considered dataset, Table 1 shows the empirical Variance-to-Mean ratios in the different time slots and for different interval amplitudes. It can be seen how the index increases with the amplitude, so overdispersion turns out quite significant for large values of τ . Also, as τ increases, and because of the aggregation of data, the sample sizes decrease. As a result, some values of the index of overdispersion cannot be calculated and correspond to empty spaces in the table.

Table 1: Overdispersion Index

τ	G_1	G_2	G_3	G_4	G_5	G_6
0.2	1.418	1.193	1.333	1.071	1.386	1.260
0.4	1.892	1.312	1.525	1.191	1.737	2.036
0.6	2.441	1.531	2.081	1.877	1.618	1.845
0.8	3.333	1.488	1.964	2.101	2.290	2.259
1	3.103	2.206	2.025	2.591	2.606	2.990
2	4.579	3.49	2.526	–	3.777	4.011
3	–	–	3.948	–	5.276	–

The data also present a positive association between arrival counts, according to Property P3. For example, for time slot G_3 , the left (respectively, right) panel of Figure 3 depicts the number of arrivals before 14h (respectively, 15h) versus the number of arrivals after 14h (15h). Each point represents a working day. The correlation coefficients were found to be 0.599 (left) and 0.658 (right).

Figure 3: Scatterplots of the number of arrivals before and after 14h (left panel) and 15h (right panel).

From the previous analyses it is evident that the Poisson process is not a proper model for the arrival process in the considered dataset, a fact already pointed out by previous studies. In this paper, we will consider a *MAP* which allows for overdispersion and non-negligible correlation between arrival counts. Specifically, the real inter-arrival times shall be fitted by a *MAP*₂ which, as illustrated in Subsection 4.3, provides a reasonable balance between the goodness of the fit and the model parsimony. The strategy for predicting the queueing quantities of interest would be to consider the fit of different *MAP*₂s according to the variations in the arrival rate, that is, one fitted *MAP*₂ to each time slot.

Concerning the services times of customers who do not abandon the system, (s_1, s_2, \dots) , Brown et al. [2005] already pointed out that the *LN* distribution is a proper choice to fit the data. Here, we have compared the performance of the *LN* distribution with a typical, heavy-tailed probability model, the Weibull distribution which is characterized (as the *LN*) by two parameters. The phase-type (*PH*) distribution is known to be a versatile model (dense, indeed, in the class of distributions in the positive half-line) that leads to tractable queueing systems using the so-called Matrix-Analytic methods, see for example He [2014]. Therefore, we have also tested the performance of the *PH* distribution of order 2, the *PH*(2), which is the simplest class of *PH* distribution and it is characterized by 5 parameters. For a complete description of the considered probability models, we refer the reader to Section 5 of the Supplementary Material. Figure 4 shows the fit provided by the three different probability models, *LN*, Weibull and *PH*(2) to the empirical distribution function of the service times regarding the time slot G_1 . In this case, the *LN* and Weibull perform similarly, and both outperform the *PH*(2). This is an expected result since the *PH* distribution is known to be light-tailed, see Bladt and Yslas [2022] where

some heavy-tailed variants of the PH distribution are proposed. Similar fits, obtained for the rest of time slots G_2, \dots, G_6 , can be seen in Figure 2 of the Supplementary Material (Section 6).

Figure 4: Fit to the service times for time slot G_1 under the LN , Weibull and $PH(2)$ distributions.

To complete the analysis we undertook a similar approach as in Brown et al. [2005] and ran the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for each one of the considered probability models and time slot. As Brown et al. [2005] already commented, the null hypothesis is rejected for many cases. However, as it can be seen from Table 2, the statistics from the test evidence a better fit by the LN model.

Probability model	G_1	G_2	G_3	G_4	G_5	G_6
LN	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.05
Weibull	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.07
$PH(2)$	0.10	0.13	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.10

Table 2: Value of the Kolmogorov- Smirnov goodness-of-fit test statistic

The real dataset also contains information regarding the waiting times before either entering service or leaving the system due to impatience, (q_1, q_2, \dots) . Note that the customers' impatience times (y_1, y_2, \dots) equal the waiting times for people who abandon the system but is (right) censored for customers who are finally served. The Birbaum-Saunders (BS) distribution, described in Section 5 of the Supplementary Material, was found to be a suitable model for the considered data. Figure 2 depicts the fit to the empirical distribution of the (censored) impatience times (slot G_1), by both the BS and the $PH(2)$ models. The (analogous) results for the rest of time slots are depicted by Figure 3 of the Supplementary Material (Section 6).

Figure 5: Fit to the impatience times for time slot G_1 under the BS and $PH(2)$ distributions.

3 The arrival process

The *MAP* [Neuts, 1979] constitutes a class of Markov renewal process that generalize in matrix form the Poisson process by allowing for dependent and non-exponentially distributed inter-arrival times. The *MAP* has been considered as a versatile stochastic model in a variety of real life contexts as teletraffic, reliability, finance, insurance or climatology, see for example Scott and Smyth [2003], Casale et al. [2010], Cheung and Landriault [2010], Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2021], Rodríguez et al. [2015], Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2014]. This section summarizes the main properties of the *MAP*, with special emphasis on the inter-arrival time distribution and the counting process.

3.1 The *MAP*: definition and main properties

Formally, a m -state *MAP*, noted MAP_m , is a doubly stochastic process $\{J(t), N(t)\}$, where $J(t)$ represents an irreducible, continuous-time, Markov process with finite state space $\mathcal{S} = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, and $N(t)$ is a counting process that accounts for the number of arrivals occurred in $(0, t]$. The MAP_m is characterized by the rate matrices $\{D_0, D_1\}$ of dimension $m \times m$ each which govern, respectively, transitions without and with the occurrence of an arrival. For more details see, for example He [2014] (Chapter 2).

The stationary *MAP* is a Markov renewal process, see [Çinlar, 1975]. If S_n denote the state of the *MAP* at the time of the n th arrival, and T_n denotes the time between the $(n - 1)$ th and n th arrivals, then $\{S_{n-1}, \sum_{i=1}^n T_i\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is a Markov renewal process. In particular, $\{S_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ is a Markov chain with transition matrix P^* given by

$$P^* = (-D_0)^{-1} D_1. \quad (3.1)$$

From the applied point of view, it will usually be the case that only a sequence of inter-arrival times are observed and that the corresponding state sequence of the *MAP* is not. Therefore, it is of interest to consider the distribution of the variable T , representing the time between two successive arrivals (inter-arrival time) in the stationary version of a *MAP*. It is known [Chakravorthy, 2001] that T is phase-type distributed with representation $\{\phi, D_0\}$, where $\phi = (\phi, 1 - \phi)$ is the probability distribution satisfying

$$\phi P^* = \phi, \quad (3.2)$$

and \mathbf{e} is a row vector with all its components equal to one. The moments of T are

$$\mu_n = E(T^n) = n! \phi (-D_0)^{-n} \mathbf{e}^T. \quad (3.3)$$

Finally, the inter-arrival times in a stationary *MAP* are known to be dependent according to the autocorrelation function

$$\rho_T(k) = \rho(T_l, T_{k+l}) = \frac{\boldsymbol{\pi} \left((-D_0)^{-1} D \right)^k (-D_0)^{-1} \mathbf{e} - \mu_1}{2\boldsymbol{\pi} (-D_0)^{-1} \mathbf{e} - \mu_1}, \quad l \geq 1. \quad (3.4)$$

Heindl et al. [2006] studies, for the case of the *MAP*₂, bounds for both the coefficient of variation of T and for ρ_1 , being $\rho_1 = \rho_T(1)$ as in (3.4). In particular, they prove that $|\rho_1| \leq 0.5$.

We summarize next the main theoretical properties about the counting process in a *MAP*. Figure 3.1 depicts the evolution of the number of arrivals occurred up to time t with that on the underlying Markov process $J(t)$ for the case of a *MAP*₂. Note that transitions of $J(t)$ between the same state always imply an increase of the counting process, but only certain transitions between different states lead to the occurrence of an arrival.

If $N(t, t + \tau)$ denotes the number of arrivals in the time interval $(t, t + \tau]$, then $N(\tau) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N(t, t + \tau)$ represents the number of arrivals in an interval of length τ in the stationary version of the process. In this case, it is known that

$$E[N(\tau)] = \lambda^* \tau, \quad (3.5)$$

where $\lambda^* = \mu_1^{-1}$ is the arrival rate, see Neuts and Li [1997]. Also,

$$\begin{aligned} V[N(\tau)] &= (\lambda^* - 2(\lambda^*)^2 - 2\boldsymbol{\pi} D_1 (D - \mathbf{e}\boldsymbol{\pi})^{-1} D_1 \mathbf{e}) \tau + \\ &\quad + 2\boldsymbol{\pi} D_1 (D - \mathbf{e}\boldsymbol{\pi})^{-1} (e^{D\tau} - I) (D - \mathbf{e}\boldsymbol{\pi})^{-1} D_1 \mathbf{e}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

As commented in Section 2, the counting process in a *MAP* presents overdispersion in the sense that (3.6) may be significantly larger than (3.5). We refer the reader to Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2021] for more details in this respect.

Figure 6: Evolution of the MAP_2 counting process $N(t)$ (blue line) with respect the underlying Markov process $J(t)$ (red line).

Finally, it is known that the increments in the counting process in a MAP are correlated. In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\tau, s) &= Cov[N(\tau), N(s)] \\ &= D_1(D-)^{-1}(e^{D\tau} - I)(e^{Ds} - I)(D-)^{-1}D_1, \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

from which the correlation is easily derived.

For more details concerning the MAP counting process, we refer the reader to Narayana and Neuts [1992], Nielsen et al. [2007], Artalejo and Gómez-Corral [2010], Neuts and Li [1997] or He [2014] (Chapter 2).

3.2 New properties of the counting process of a MAP

As illustrated by Figure 2 regarding the real dataset, the correlation of the counts between consecutive intervals may be non-negligible. Even though the expression for the covariance function as in (3.7) of the counting process of a MAP has been known from long ago, there is not any study devoted to look into its characteristics, up to our knowledge. To such aim, we define the covariance and correlation functions between two intervals of the same length τ as

$$C(\tau) = \varphi(\tau, \tau) \quad (3.8)$$

$$R(\tau) = \frac{C(\tau)}{V[N(\tau)]}, \quad (3.9)$$

where $V[N(\tau)]$ is the variance defined in (3.6). The next two results establish the sign and monotony of the covariance function in terms of the inter-arrival times first-lag autocorre-

lation function of a MAP_2 . In general, MAP processes are over-parametrized since it may be the case that two different MAP representations $\{D_0, D_1\}$ and $\{\tilde{D}_0, \tilde{D}_1\}$ lead to the same likelihood function for all sequences of observed inter-arrival times $\mathbf{t} = (t_1, \dots, t_n)$, $n \geq 1$, [Rydén, 1996]. However, the two-state MAP (MAP_2) can be represented by a canonical, unique parametrization in terms of four parameters, as shown by Bodrog et al. [2008]. In particular, if $-1 \leq \gamma < 1$ is the eigenvalue different from 1 of the transition matrix P^* as in (3.1), then when $\gamma \geq 0$ the canonical form of the MAP_2 (*first canonical form*) is given by

$$D_0 = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ 0 & u \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -x - y & 0 \\ v & -u - v \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.10)$$

On the other hand, for those MAP_2 s such that $\gamma < 0$, then their canonical form (*second canonical form*) is

$$D_0 = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ 0 & u \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -x - y \\ -u - v & v \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.11)$$

The previous canonical forms of the MAP_2 shall be considered in the proof of the theoretical results. For the sake of brevity, such proofs can be found in the Supplementary Material.

Proposition 1. *Let a MAP_2 be represented with a first canonical form as in (3.10). Let $C(\tau)$ and $\rho = \rho_T(1)$ denote the covariance function and first-lag autocorrelation coefficient of the inter-arrival times as in (3.8) and (3.4), respectively. Then,*

1. $\rho > 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) > 0$ and $C'(\tau) > 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.
2. $\rho = 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) = 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.
3. $\rho < 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) < 0$ and $C'(\tau) < 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.

Proposition 2. *Let a MAP_2 be represented with a second canonical form as in (3.11). Let $C(\tau)$ and $\rho = \rho_T(1)$ denote the covariance function and first-lag autocorrelation coefficient of the inter-arrival times as in (3.8) and (3.4), respectively. Then,*

1. $\rho > 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) < 0$ and $C'(\tau) < 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.
2. $\rho = 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) = 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.
3. $\rho < 0 \Rightarrow C(\tau) > 0$ and $C'(\tau) > 0$, for all $\tau > 0$.

Two interesting remarks result from Propositions 1 and 2. First, the covariance function $C(\tau)$ is either positive, negative or zero, for all $\tau > 0$. Second, the relationship

between the correlation of consecutive inter-arrival times, ρ , and the dependence structure of the counting process is clear: the sign of ρ determines the sign and monotony of $C(\tau)$.

The next result concerning the correlation function $R(\tau)$ of a *MAP* is general and does not limit to the two-state case.

Proposition 3. *Let $R(\tau)$ as in (3.9) denote the correlation function in a general m -state MAP. Then,*

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} R(\tau) = 0.$$

In order to analyze more in depth the forms of (3.8) and (3.9) we carried out a simulation experiment where a total of 10000 *MAP*₂ representations $\{D_0, D_1\}$ from both canonical forms (3.10) and (3.11), and for both cases $\rho > 0$ and $\rho < 0$. Figure 7 depicts some selected different patterns concerning the covariance function $C(\tau)$.

Figure 7: Patterns for the covariance function $C(\tau)$. *Top panels:* first canonical form. *Bottom panels:* Second canonical form. Left panels: $\rho > 0$ Right panels: $\rho < 0$.

In similar way, Figure 8 displays some observed patterns of the correlation function $R(\tau)$. Note that both Figures 7 and 8 are consistent with the theoretical results stated previously.

It is interesting to note that when $R(\tau)$ is positive then, values close to 1 may be observed.

However, if $R(\tau)$ is negative the attained values remain close to 0. It is an open question to look into this phenomenon and study the existence of upper and lower bounds for $R(\tau)$.

Figure 8: Patterns for the correlation function $R(\tau)$. *Top panels*: first canonical form. *Bottom panels*: Second canonical form. Left panels: $\rho > 0$ Right panels: $\rho < 0$.

4 Inference for the arrival process

Given a set of traces of inter-arrival times defining the arrival process in a queue, the aim is to fit a *MAP* to the sample. For simplicity we focus on the fit provided by the MAP_2 and in particular, due to the positive correlation between arrivals counts in a time partition, we focus on the first canonical form as in (3.10), which is associated to positive correlation patterns, see Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2017].

4.1 Previous approaches

Statistical inference for *MAPs* has been widely considered in the literature from different perspectives, either from moments matching approaches [Bodrog et al., 2008, Casale

et al., 2010, Rodríguez et al., 2015, Yera et al., 2019], direct maximization of the likelihood function [Ramírez-Cobo et al., 2021], EM algorithm [Breuer, 2002, Okamura and Dohi, 2016] or Bayesian inference [Scott and Smyth, 2003, Fearnhead and Sherlock, 2006, Ramírez-Cobo et al., 2017]. See Buchholz et al. [2014] for a good summary of inference approaches for *MAPs*. In the previous works the sample information is assumed to be given by a single sample of inter-arrival times $\mathbf{t} = \{t_1, \dots, t_N\}$ and the different inference approaches focus on the inter-arrival time distribution. However, less approaches have considered the inclusion of the counting process in the estimation method. Some examples are Eum et al. [2007], Nasr et al. [2018], Okamura et al. [2009], Breuer and Kume [2010].

Given the nature of the dataset described in Section 2 the sample information concerning the arrival process consists in N samples of inter-arrival times,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{t}^{(1)} &= (t_1^{(1)}, t_2^{(1)}, \dots, t_{n_1}^{(1)}), \\ \mathbf{t}^{(2)} &= (t_1^{(2)}, t_2^{(2)}, \dots, t_{n_2}^{(2)}), \\ &\vdots \\ \mathbf{t}^{(N)} &= (t_1^{(N)}, t_2^{(N)}, \dots, t_{n_N}^{(N)}). \end{aligned}$$

Up to our knowledge, the only previous work dealing with estimation of *MAP*₂s in a multiple sample framework is Rodríguez et al. [2015], which is based on a moments-matching method. We propose a novel, two-stages, estimation method that extends Rodríguez et al. [2015] by considering information of the correlation function $R(\tau)$ as in (3.9). The method in Rodríguez et al. [2015] is theoretically supported by Bodrog et al. [2008] which proves that the *MAP*₂ is characterized by four inter-arrival descriptors, namely, the first, second and third moments of T , μ_1, μ_2, μ_3 , as in (3.3) and the first-lag autocorrelation coefficient, $\rho = \rho_T(1)$ as in (3.4). Specifically, Rodríguez et al. [2015] propose to minimize the following objective function

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(\boldsymbol{\theta}) &= (\rho(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\rho})^2 + \\ &+ \left(\frac{\mu_1(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_1}{\bar{\mu}_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_2(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_2}{\bar{\mu}_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_3(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_3}{\bar{\mu}_3} \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (x, y, u, v)$ are the components of D_0 and D_1 , and $(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2, \bar{\mu}_3, \bar{\rho})$ are the counterparts of the characterizing descriptors. Specifically,

$$\bar{\mu}_m = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} (t_i^{(j)})^m}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_j}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3,$$

and $\bar{\rho}$, is given by the median of the empirical autocorrelation coefficients of the 1% of the longest samples $\mathbf{t}^{(i)}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. The solution to the previous minimization problem is noted as $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$.

Figure 9: Empirical (solid line) versus estimated (dotted line) correlation function $R(\tau)$.

However, in practice, the descriptors $(\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \rho)$ may not be good enough to properly approximate the counting process in a MAP_2 , as the following numerical example illustrates. Consider the MAP_2 defined by

$$D_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -0.81 & 0.04 \\ 0 & -5.88 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.76 & 0 \\ 0.09 & 5.79 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.2)$$

A total of 50 traces of length equal to 100 were simulated and the empirical moments $(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2, \bar{\mu}_3, \bar{\rho}) = (0.377, 0.714, 2.352, 0.308)$ were used as input to fit the MAP_2 according to Rodríguez et al. [2015]. As a result, the four empirical moments were perfectly recovered by the estimated model $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$, that is $(\hat{\mu}_1, \hat{\mu}_2, \hat{\mu}_3, \hat{\rho}) = (\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2, \bar{\mu}_3, \bar{\rho})$. However, the parameters of the generator model $\{D_0, D_1\}$ were not fully recovered:

$$\hat{D}_0(0) = \begin{pmatrix} -0.90 & 0.12 \\ 0 & -11.80 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1(0) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.78 & 0 \\ 0.60 & 11.20 \end{pmatrix}.$$

This is not a surprising result since the variability in the sampled inter-arrival times results in (slight) differences between the theoretical moments $(\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \rho)$ and the empirical ones, in this case $(\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \rho) = (0.409, 0.732, 2.573, 0.326)$. As a result of this discrepancy, other descriptors not considered in the objective function (4.1) may not be well estimated. For example, Figure 9 depicts the empirical correlation function (in solid line), $R(\tau)$, and the estimated function (dotted line), computed from $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$.

4.2 The new method

Since in this work we are interested in capturing the properties of call center data (in particular, some of the correlations $R(\tau)$ showed by Figure 2), we propose a modification

of the method in [Ramírez-Cobo et al., 2021] and additionally consider descriptors of the counting process. In particular, we formulate a new objective function

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta_{\boldsymbol{\beta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, (\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*)) &= \beta_1(\rho(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\rho})^2 + \\
&+ \beta_1 \left(\left(\frac{\mu_1(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_1}{\bar{\mu}_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_2(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_2}{\bar{\mu}_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_3(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \bar{\mu}_3}{\bar{\mu}_3} \right)^2 \right) + \\
&+ \beta_2 \sum_{i=1}^k (R(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \tau_i^*) - \bar{R}(\tau_i^*))^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

where β_1 and β_2 are tuning parameters. Note that (4.3) is expressed in similar way as (4.1), but also considers new terms regarding the empirical correlation function $R(\tau)$. The optimization problem to be solved is stated as

$$(P) \begin{cases} \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=(x,y,u,v)} & \delta_{\boldsymbol{\beta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, (\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*)) \\ \text{s.t.} & y, v \geq 0, \\ & x, u \leq 0, \\ & x + y \leq 0, \\ & u + v \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

The choice of a starting solution to initialize (P) is essential in order to ease the computational cost. In this case we take benefit from Ramírez-Cobo et al. [2021] and use as starting points the values $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$ that minimize (4.1). Then, problem (P) is solved for each pair $(\beta_1, \beta_2) \in I \times J$ where, in our experiments, $I = \{2^{-10}, 2^{-9}, \dots, 2^{14}, 2^{15}\}$ and $J = \{2^1, 2^2, \dots, 2^{14}, 2^{15}\}$ have been set. Among all obtained solutions, the final estimate $\{\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1\}$ is selected as the one that makes $\delta_{\boldsymbol{\beta}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, (\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*))$ to attain the lowest value. Algorithm 1 summarizes the new approach.

Algorithm 1 Inference approach for the MAP_2

Input:

- Characterizing empirical moments $(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2, \bar{\mu}_3, \bar{\rho})$ obtained from the sample of inter-arrival times.
- Starting solution: $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$ that minimizes (4.1).
- Sequence of amplitudes $\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*$.
- Grid for tuning parameters: $\beta_1 \in I, \beta_2 \in J$.

Output:

- Final estimate $\{\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1\}$.

for $i \in I$ **do****for** $j \in J$ **do**

1. $\beta_1 = I(i), \beta_2 = J(j), \boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \beta_2)$. Solve problem (P) with $\{\hat{D}_0(0), \hat{D}_1(0)\}$ as starting solution.
2. Save the solution $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(i, j)$.

end for**end for**

$$(\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{u}, \hat{v}) = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{(i,j)}, \quad i \in I, j \in J \delta \boldsymbol{\beta}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, (\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*)),$$

$$\hat{D}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{x} & \hat{y} \\ 0 & \hat{u} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -\hat{x} - \hat{y} & 0 \\ \hat{v} & -\hat{u} - \hat{v} \end{pmatrix}$$

As an illustration of the method, consider the simulated example presented in 4.2. For the sake of comparison, problem (P) has been run under three different scenarios, namely, when $k = 1$ (using $\tau_1^* = 1$), when $k = 3$ (using $\tau_1^* = 0.5, \tau_2^* = 1, \tau_3^* = 1.5$) and $k = 5$ (using $\tau_1^* = 0.5, \tau_2^* = 1, \tau_3^* = 1.5, \tau_4^* = 2, \tau_5^* = 2.5$). Figure 10 is the analogous version of Figure 9 obtained under the new approach. It can be seen from the figure how the fit has improved with the increase of k . For more details concerning the fit of this synthetic dataset, we refer the reader to Subsection 4.1 of the Supplementary Material.

To end this subsection it is important to comment that the choice of the amplitudes $\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*$ and of k itself is arbitrary and for the previous example, other and possibly better values could have been selected. The study of optimal amplitudes is an open problem out of the scope of this work that shall will be considered in future work.

4.3 Performance on the real dataset

The primary goal of this paper is to infer quantities of interest of the queue generated by the real dataset described in Section 2. For that, as commented in Section 2, inter-

Figure 10: Empirical correlation function $R(\tau)$ (solid line) and fits under the new approach (dotted red, green and black lines) and under the approach only based on inter-arrival moments (dotted blue line).

arrival, service and impatience times are fitted by the MAP_2 , LN distribution and BS distribution, respectively. This subsection presents a summary of the most illustrating results about how the estimation method described in Subsection 4.2 performs for the Anonymous dataset and refer the reader to the Supplementary Material for complementary details. It is important to firstly remark that the traces of the real inter-arrival times are not characterized by high or extreme values of either the first-lag autocorrelation coefficient or coefficient of variation. Indeed, for all cases the empirical correlation coefficient was found to be less than 0.5 and therefore, according to Heindl et al. [2006], there is no need to consider the fit by higher-order $MAPs$ which are more versatile but also lead to more complexity in the inference process.

We concentrate here on the results obtained for the second time slot G_2 which, according to Figure 1, concentrates the most intense activity of the call center. Algorithm 1 described in the previous subsection was run and, for the sake of comparison, three different choices of k (number of amplitudes, see Algorithm 1) were considered. First, $k = 1$ was set, with the choice of the amplitude equal to 0.25, that is, $\tau_1^* = 0.25$. Second, k was set to 3, and $\tau_1^* = 0.25$, $\tau_2^* = 0.5$ and $\tau_3^* = 0.75$ were used. Finally, k was set to 5 and the values $\tau_1^* = 0.25$, $\tau_2^* = 0.5$, $\tau_3^* = 0.75$, $\tau_4^* = 1$, $\tau_5^* = 1.25$ were used. For each case, the obtained estimates (\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1) were used to fit the empirical cdfs of the inter-arrival times for three random selected days (the 5th, the 20th and the 32th), see Figure 11. Two comments arise from the figure. First, the performance of the fitted model is pretty good for the 5th and 20th days, and a bit poorer for the 32th day. Similar performances for the rest of days were observed. Second, it is clear that the choice of k does not seem to affect

Figure 11: Empirical (solid line) and fitted (dotted line) cumulative distribution function of the inter-arrival times between 9 and 11 am of the 5th, 20th and 32th days.

the fit, since the estimated cdf is almost undistinguishable among the three considered scenarios ($k = 1, 3, 5$). This also occurs for the rest of the considered days in the study.

If the interest is in the fit that the estimated MAP_2 provides to the counting process descriptors Table 3 shows, for a grid of amplitudes ranging from 0.1 to 1, the empirical values for the expected number of arrivals, the variance, the correlation function and the index of overdispersion (Variance-to-Mean ratio) and their fitted counterparts for each of the considered scenarios ($k = 1, 3, 5$). The analogous tables to Table 3 corresponding to the rest of time slots can be found in Subsection 4.2 of the Supplementary Material. From the table it can be seen that, unlike the case of a synthetic dataset as the considered in Subsection 4.2, higher values of k do not necessarily lead to better estimators here. Indeed, from the table it can be seen how the performance of the fit is not homogeneous among the considered descriptors, neither in terms of τ nor in terms of k . For example, for $\tau = 0.3$, $E[N(\tau)]$ is better estimated than $R(\tau)$; however, for $\tau = 0.8$, the situation is the inverse: the fit for $R(\tau)$ outperforms that of $E[N(\tau)]$. In similar way, the choice of $k = 5$ seems to be better for fitting $E[N(0.3)]$ but $k = 1$ is better for $R(0.5)$. Thus, given a real dataset, it is not possible to state a priori which choice of k and τ 's leads to the best performance of the method, and therefore a tuning process as the undertaken in this subsection is suggested. Then, the user will need to select the most appropriate

setting options in terms of her fitting priorities. From a computational cost viewpoint, the suggested tuning approach is computationally inexpensive: for the dataset considered here the whole procedure took few minutes for an intermediate quality computer.

Table 3: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the second slot G_2 (9-11h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.1		10.475		12.357		0.147		1.180
	10.568	10.431	10.126	11.862	0.119	0.121	0.958	1.137
		10.534		12.512		0.125		1.188
0.2		20.950		28.354		0.244		1.353
	21.625	20.863	25.798	26.585	0.267	0.215	1.193	1.274
		21.069		28.148		0.22		1.336
0.3		31.425		47.812		0.31		1.521
	31.932	31.294	38.205	44.167	0.39	0.291	1.196	1.411
		31.603		46.880		0.295		1.483
0.4		41.9		70.562		0.356		1.684
	44.273	41.725	58.065	64.607	0.374	0.354	1.312	1.548
		42.138		68.680		0.354		1.630
0.5		52.375		96.443		0.388		1.841
	53.114	52.156	82.304	87.901	0.372	0.406	1.550	1.685
		52.672		93.519		0.403		1.775
0.6		62.850		125.301		0.41		1.994
	61.568	62.588	94.258	114.050	0.554	0.450	1.531	1.822
		63.207		121.369		0.443		1.920
0.7		73.326		156.989		0.424		2.141
	67.523	73.019	103.765	143.050	0.512	0.488	1.537	1.959
		73.741		152.203		0.477		2.064
0.8		83.801		191.370		0.508		2.284
	79.341	83.450	118.044	174.900	0.501	0.521	1.488	2.096
		84.275		185.994		0.505		2.207
0.9		94.276		228.312		0.439		2.422
	95.580	93.881	210.979	209.599	0.550	0.550	2.207	2.233
		94.810		222.713		0.529		2.349
1		104.751		267.687		0.442		2.555
	104.875	104.313	231.344	247.145	0.584	0.576	2.206	2.369
		105.344		262.334		0.549		2.490

5 The queueing system

It has been shown how the inter-arrival times of the Anonymous bank dataset may be modeled by a MAP_2 , a model that allows for overdispersion and correlated counts. Also, the service and impatience times are correctly fitted by a LN and BS distributions, as detailed in Section 2. This section considers inference for the queueing system where the arrival process is governed by a MAP_2 , the service process by a LN distribution, the impatience times are assumed to be distributed according to a BS distributions and a finite number of servers is considered. From a theoretical viewpoint, such queue lacks closed form expressions for the steady-state distributions of interest (queue length and virtual waiting time). Therefore, the estimation of the systems is carried out via simulation of the associated components. The section is structured as follows. First, Subsection 5.1, gives the main definitions associated to the considered queue. Subsection 5.2, describes a simulator for the considered queue: given the parameters of the governing MAP_2 , LN and BS distributions and the number of servers C , the methods generates traces of inter-arrival, service and impatience times, waiting times, and times spent in the system for a desired number of customers. From the simulated samples, a comparison study can be undertaken to evaluate how the estimated waiting times and queue length distributions, and the abandon rates change with the value of C . Such results are presented in Subsection 5.3.

5.1 The $MAP_2/LN/C$ queueing system with impatience times

Assume a first in-first out queueing system with a finite number C of identical servers. The arrival process is governed by a MAP_2 with rate matrices (D_0, D_1) and let X be the random variable denoting the arrival time. Because the MAP_2 characterizes the arrival process, then the inter-arrival times are PH-distributed. The service times are independent and identically distributed as a random variable $S \sim LN(\mu, \sigma)$. Customers entering the system may leave before starting their service. As commented in the previous sections, the impatience time distribution, denoted by Y , shall be assumed to be of type BS with parameters (α, β) . The random variables X, S, Y are assumed to be independent. In addition, let Z and Q be the random variables representing the departure time from the system and the waiting time before either entering service or leaving the system (without having started their service).

We assume that the queueing system is stable which implies that the stationary distributions of the queue lengths and waiting times exists. In particular, let $L(t)$ represent the number of customers waiting in the queue at time t . Then, for $j \geq 0$,

$$\pi_j = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} P[L(t) = j], \quad (5.1)$$

represents the steady-state distribution of the queue length at an arbitrary time. Also, consider the waiting time distribution function denoted by $F_W(t)$ and defined as the

probability that at an arbitrary time, a virtual customer who arrives at that time waits at most a time t before entering service. If I is the indicator variable taking the value 1 if the customer enters service (and 0 if the customer abandons before entering service), then $W \stackrel{d}{=} (Q \mid I = 1)$. Closed-form expressions for the generating functions of L and for the Laplace-Stieltjes transform of W for the considered queueing system have not been found, to the best of our knowledge. For this reason, inference for the queueing system generated by the "Anonymous Bank" dataset shall be undertaken via a simulation-based approach, described in the next subsection.

5.2 A simulator of the queue

A queueing system as that of the previous subsection can be described by a sequence of random variables. If $i \geq 1$ denote the customer, $\{x_i\}$ represents the arrival time, obtained from the inter-arrival times as $x_i = \sum_{j=1}^i t_j$. Sequences $\{s_i\}$ and $\{y_i\}$ denote the service and impatience times. Finally, $\{z_i\}$ and $\{q_i\}$, realizations of the random variables Z and Q , will represent the departures times and waiting times before either entering service or leaving the system. It is assumed that, initially, the servers are free, so that customers $1, \dots, C$ start service on arrival. Therefore, for these customers $q_i = 0$ and $z_i = x_i + s_i$. For a general customer i , with $i > C$, if any server is free at x_i , then i starts service immediately (and $q_i = 0$ and $z_i = x_i + s_i$). Otherwise, let u represent the time that i has to wait before entering service. If the customer has not started service after a waiting a time y_i (that is, if $y_i < u$), then she leaves impatiently without being served at all. In this case, $q_i = y_i$ and $z_i = x_i + y_i$. Otherwise, i commences service after waiting a time $q_i = u < y_i$ and $z_i = x_i + q_i + s_i$. For the sake of clarity, this behavior can be visualized in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Behavior of the $MAP_2/LN/C$ queueing system with impatient customers.

As pointed out in Subsection 5.1, there are not closed-form expressions for computing either the steady-state queue length or waiting time distributions. Therefore, we propose to infer such quantities through a simulation approach where, given the parameters characterizing the arrival and services process and the impatience distribution, random sequences as those described above are generated. Table 4 summarizes both the input and output arguments of the proposed simulator. The outputs have all been described before except for the auxiliary variable $\mathbf{r}(h)$ ($h \in \{1, \dots, C\}$) that quantifies the time until server h releases. This vector is updated each time any server is occupied.

Finally, Table 5 provides the pseudo-code for generating the samples of interest. The procedure replicates the behavior of the queue that has been described at the beginning of this subsection. Given the parameters defining the arrival and service process as well as the distribution for the impatience times, number of servers and desired number of customers, first sequences of length n of arrival, impatience and service time are simulated. Note that although n service times are simulated, at the end of the process such number becomes lower since there a set of customer who abandon the system without being served.

Lines 4 – 5 refers to the first C customers, which do not need to queue and enter directly into service. The process for the subsequent customers (lines 6-32) is based on the existence of any empty server. If at the arrival time x_i of customer i there is an empty server then i directly enters service and does not wait any time. If, on the contrary, all

Table 4: Inputs and outputs of the simulator of the $MAP_2/LN/C$ queue with impatience times

1. **Inputs:**

$\{D_0, D_1\}$ (MAP_2)

(μ, σ) (LN service times)

(α, β) (BS impatience times)

C (number of servers)

n (number of customers to be simulated)

2. **Outputs:**

$x_i, i = 1, \dots, n$ (arrival times)

$y_i, i = 1, \dots, n$ (impatience times)

$\mathbf{I}(i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \text{ enters service} \\ 0 & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases} \quad p = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{I}(i)$

$s_i, i = 1, \dots, p$ (service times)

$z_i, i = 1, \dots, n$ (time spent in the system)

$q_i, i = 1, \dots, n$ (queueing waiting times)

$r(h), h = 1, \dots, C$ (time until the h -th server releases)

servers are busy two situations may occur. On one hand, i is the first in the queue (lines 12 – 18). In this case, the time u that i must wait in order to enter service is computed and compared with the impatience of i . As a result of such comparison, i may either leave (and therefore, s_i is erased) or stay to receive service. On the other hand, i may encounter at her arrival other customers who are queueing. In this case, it is necessary to identify which of these queueing customers will abandon the system. If all the queueing customers abandon, then the situation is analogous to that described by lines 14 – 15. If this is not the case, the value of u , which again represents the time that i must wait in order to enter service, needs to be calculated. Such calculation depends of the waiting time of the queueing customer that will enter service before i (noted as j in the pseudo-code). Then, such time u is compared to the impatience time of i . As a result, the decision of leaving or staying is taken and all quantities are updated accordingly.

Note that the pseudo-code could have been summarized without taking into account the position of i in the queue at the time of her arrival. Simply, the variable u needs to

be calculated and compared to y_i . However, the computation of u is a bit more tricky in case of the existence of queueing customers at the arrival of i . This is the reason this extended version of the pseudo-code has been shown.

Table 5: Pseudo-code of the simulator of the $MAP_2/LN/C$ queue with impatience times

1. From $\{D_0, D_1\}$ simulate the arrival times (x_1, \dots, x_n)
2. From $\{\alpha, \beta\}$ simulate the impatience times (y_1, \dots, y_n)
3. From $\{\mu, \sigma\}$ simulate the service times (s_1, \dots, s_n)
4. **For** $i = 1, \dots, C$ **do**:
5. $q_i = 0, z_i = x_i + s_i, \mathbf{r}(i) = x_i + s_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 1$
6. **For** $i = C + 1, \dots, n$ **do**:
7. $\mathbf{E} = \text{find}(\mathbf{r} < x_i)$ {identify the empty servers}
8. **If** $\text{length}(\mathbf{E}) > 0$ **then** {at least there is an empty server}
9. $q_i = 0, z_i = x_i + s_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 1$
10. $h = \min(\mathbf{E}), \mathbf{r}(h) = x_i + s_i$
11. **Else** {all servers are busy}
12. **If** i is the first in queue **then**
13. $u = \min(\mathbf{r}) - x_i$ {time that i must wait to enter service}
14. **If** $u > y_i$ { i abandons} **then**
15. $q_i = y_i, z_i = x_i + y_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 0, s_i = []$
16. **Else** { i will enter service}
17. $q_i = u, z_i = x_i + q_i + s_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 1$
18. $h = \min(\mathbf{r}), \mathbf{r}(h) = x_i + q_i + s_i$
19. **Else** { i is not the first in queue}
20. Identify the set of queueing customers $\{i - 1, \dots, i - l\}$
21. Calculate $m =$ # queueing customers that will enter
service
22. **If** $m = 0$ {all queueing customers will abandon}
23. **Go to** 13-18
24. **Else** {at least one queueing customer will enter service}

25. Find $j = \text{last queueing customer that will enter service}$
26. $u = q(j) + \min(\mathbf{r}) - x_i$
27. **If** $u > y_i$ **{** i **abandons}** **then**
28. $q_i = y_i, z_i = x_i + y_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 0, s_i = []$
29. **Else** **{** i **will enter service}**
30. $q_i = \min(\mathbf{r}) - x_i$
31. $z_i = x_i + q_i + s_i, \mathbf{I}(i) = 1$
32. $h = \min(\mathbf{r}), \mathbf{r}(h) = x_i + q_i + s_i$

5.3 Estimated performance of the queueing system

Consider now the "Anonymous bank" dataset, described by samples $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$ and $\mathbf{q} = (q_1, \dots, q_n)$, with $n = 42616$. The ultimate goal of this study is to use such sample information to infer the steady state distributions of both the queue length, L , and waiting time, W , defined in Subsection 5.1. As it will be seen, the distributions will be estimated and compared for a variety of number of servers, C . Also, the proportion of customers who abandon the system before entering service shall be estimated. The procedure for this analysis is described next. First, each customer (call) must be located in one of the considered time slots $G_1 - G_6$. Samples corresponding to time slot G_l , say $\mathbf{x}_l, \mathbf{s}_l$ and \mathbf{q}_l , each of length g_l , for $l = 1, \dots, 6$ ($g_1 + \dots + g_6 = 42616$) will be used to fit the corresponding MAP_2 , LN and BS parameters: $(\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1)_l, (\hat{\mu}, \hat{\sigma})_l, (\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})_l$. This implies that, for this particular dataset, the simulator described by Table 4 is run a total of six times (one per each time slot). Concerning the fit to the inter-arrival times, the solutions (\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1) under the choice $k = 1$ described in Subsection 4.3 were used. Then, for each $l \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$, the parameters $(\hat{D}_0, \hat{D}_1)_l, (\hat{\mu}, \hat{\sigma})_l, (\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})_l$ are the input arguments of the simulator described by Tables 3 and 4, together with a desired value of C and taking the sample size n equal to n_l . For each time slot, the simulator is run a total of 100 times, so that the queue length distribution $\{\pi_j\}_{j \geq 0}$, the waiting time distribution $F_W(t)$ and the abandon rates are estimated in frequentist way. The final estimate is obtained by averaging the quantities over the 100 simulations.

Table 6: Average abandon rates (in percentage terms)

<i>Empirical</i>	$C = 3$	$C = 5$	$C = 7$	$C = 9$	$C = 11$
G_1	5.70	6.86	0.30	0	0
G_2	22.27	42.27	21.22	7.71	2.34
G_3	14	35.20	11.30	2.88	0.42
G_4	10.77	22.23	7.99	0.39	0.14
G_5	7.25	7.96	0.69	0.01	0
G_6	6.33	4.29	0.10	0	0

The obtained results are presented next. First, Table 6 shows the empirical abandon rates along with the estimated values for 5 different choices of C . As expected, the rates decrease with the value of C . Some values have been highlighted in bold style: they represent the fits closest to the empirical abandon rates. Therefore, for the considered values of C , $C = 3$ turns out more suitable for modeling data in G_1 , G_5 and G_6 , while $C = 5$ is more appropriate for $G_2 - G_4$. We recall at this point that the information concerning the real number of servers in the system at time t for the "Anonymous bank" dataset was unclear to us, that is why we have used an assortment of values of C . We should remark here that in any case a close fit to the empirical behavior should be expected since, as has been already commented, some factors of the dataset (as for example, the customers' priorities) have non been considered in our modelization . It is interesting to note that, as expected, times slots G_2 and G_3 which, according to Figure 1, are the most intense traffic periods, present the highest abandon rates.

Figure 13 depicts the estimated virtual waiting time distribution at each time slot, using, among the considered values of C , the most likely one for each case, that is, $C = 3, 5, 5, 5, 3, 3$ for $G_1 - G_6$, respectively. It is remarkable here the fact that, for the time slot G_2 , the convergence to 1 is the slowest one, a fact that is in accordance with the most intense traffic activity (and thus, the highest waiting times and abandon rates).

Figure 13: Virtual waiting distribution under the choice of $C = 3, 5, 5, 5, 3, 3$ for $G_1 - G_6$.

In order to look at time slot G_2 in more depth, Figure 14 analyzes how the number of servers affect the virtual waiting time distribution. The impact of the increase of C is very noticeable and important for managers that take decisions concerning the system. According to Figure 14 the waiting times change considerably for small numbers of servers. However, the curves for $C = 9$ and $C = 11$ (and even $C = 7$) are almost undistinguishable which suggests that the manager should carefully calibrate the choice of C if the aim is to speed the activity and reduce abandon rates.

Figure 14: Virtual waiting time distribution for the second time slot, G_2 (9 – 11h) for an assortment of number of servers

Table 7 completes the information regarding the queue performance by showing the estimated steady-state queue length probabilities, for each time slot and different number

of servers ($C = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11$). The results are consistent with the behavior of the data: for less intense traffic periods (as G_1 , G_5 and G_6) the probability of an empty queue is higher in comparison to more active periods, even if the number of servers is small. For the most intense traffic period (G_2) the increase in the number of servers has a big impact, for example, the probability of having 6 or more calls in wait goes from 0.79, under $C = 3$, to 0.21, for $C = 5$, and to 0.03, for $C = 7$. Here again, this points towards the necessity for the decision maker to assess the trade-off between the cost of increasing the number of servers and the losses due to waiting customers.

Table 7: Steady-state queue length distribution

		π_0	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4	π_5	$\sum_{j=6}^{\infty} \pi_j$
$C = 3$	G_1	0.75	0.10	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.01
	G_2	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.79
	G_3	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.71
	G_4	0.31	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.21
	G_5	0.71	0.10	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.04
	G_6	0.88	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.01	0	0
$C = 5$	G_1	0.98	0.01	0.01	0	0	0	0
	G_2	0.37	0.12	0.10	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.21
	G_3	0.56	0.12	0.10	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.06
	G_4	0.78	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03
	G_5	0.96	0.02	0.01	0.01	0	0	0
	G_6	0.99	0.01	0	0	0	0	0
$C = 7$	G_1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_2	0.71	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.03
	G_3	0.87	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
	G_4	0.95	0.03	0.01	0.01	0	0	0
	G_5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
$C = 9$	G_1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_2	0.91	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
	G_3	0.97	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0
	G_4	0.99	0.01	0	0	0	0	0
	G_5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
$C = 11$	G_1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_2	0.93	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	G_3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	G_5	1	0	0 ³²	0	0	0	0
	G_6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Finally, Section 7 in the Supplementary Material contains practical information regarding the sensitivity of the queueing system measures with respect to the correlation coefficient of the inter-arrival times, ρ_1 .

As can be seen, taking into consideration the inter-arrival dependence significantly influences the quantities of interest of the queueing system and therefore justifies the use of models such as *MAP*.

6 Discussion

Data-driven tools have become of paramount importance for extracting knowledge and making proper decisions in a variety of contexts as Reliability, Marketing or Finance. The term *Queueing Science* encompasses a set of data-driven techniques to describe the performance of the queue generated by a given dataset using simulation and statistical modeling. This work contributes in this line by proposing a simulator that enables the user to evaluate the performance of a queueing system in terms of abandon rates, queue length and virtual time distributions. The presented data-driven method has been specifically designed for the popular "Anonymous bank" call center data, but can be easily adapted to other modern call center datasets. Indeed, the simulator can be applied in other making decision problems where dependent inter-event times have an effect over the system performance as in, for example, reliability, teletraffic or survival analysis, among others. Also the method developed in this work can be easily adapted to other types of queueing systems for which computing the quantities of interest involves solving equations and Laplace transforms that are, in many cases, computationally complicated to obtain. The simulator is based on the separate fits for the arrival and service processes and incorporates information regarding customers impatience times. As it is common for modern call center data, arrival counts of the "Anonymous bank" dataset show both overdispersion and positive correlations among arrival counts, a fact that limits the use of classical stochastic point processes. In this paper the *MAP*, a type of Markov renewal process that allows for non-exponential and dependent inter-arrival times as well as overdispersion and positively correlation arrival counts, has been considered. Respectively, service and impatience times are fitted by a *LN* and *BS* distributions. The number of servers is a free parameter that allows the managerial decision maker a direct comparison between the performance of different systems in straightforward way. Up to our knowledge, the resulting *MAP*₂/*LN*/*C* queue with impatience times has not been considered before in the literature, neither from a theoretical nor an applied point of view.

The findings of this work are not only simulation-based but also methodological. On one hand, a novel inference approach for the two-state *MAP* has been described. Unlike most of the previous fitting methods for *MAP*s, some descriptors of the counting process have been considered in combination with inter-arrival times descriptors. The inclusion of information regarding the counting process helps to better model the correlation of

the arrival counts, an important feature of call center data. On the other hand, new properties regarding the dependence structure of the counting process of the *MAP* have been derived. These results are useful for data practitioners which can decide whether or not to use the *MAP* depending on the empirical properties.

A number of possible research directions arise from this work. First, following Brown et al. [2005] it would be of interest to develop a statistical test to decide whether the arrival data sufficiently support the hypothesis of being distributed from a *MAP*. Second, for the sake of brevity, in this paper only the abandon rates, queue lengths and waiting times distributions have been calculated to measure the performance of the system but other quantities as the busy period could have been estimated. Third, it is of interest to model priority, a feature of the considered dataset that has not been addressed in our analysis. Finally, the proposed inference approach for the *MAP*₂ relies on the values of k (number of amplitudes) and the amplitudes themselves, τ^* s. The study of optimal choices is a challenging research line. Work on these issues is underway.

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Supplementary Material to “Call center data modeling: a queueing science approach based on Markovian arrival processes”

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1 Proof of Proposition 1

The first-lag autocorrelation coefficient, $\rho = \rho_T(1)$, defined by (3.4) in Section 3.1 of the main manuscript can be rewritten as

$$\rho = \gamma \frac{\mu_2 - 2\mu_1^2}{2(\mu_2 - \mu_1^2)}, \quad (1.1)$$

see Bodrog et al. [2008]. Note that $(\mu_2 - \mu_1^2)$ is the variance of the inter-arrival time T , so the denominator of (1.1) is always positive. On the other hand, consider a MAP_2 with first canonical form. Then, the numerator of (1.1) can be shown to be

$$\gamma(\mu_2 - 2\mu_1^2) = \frac{-2vy(u+v)(x+y)(u+v-x)(x-u+y)}{u^2x^2(uy+vx+vy)^2}, \quad (1.2)$$

where, from the definition of the elements of D_0 and D_1 , $vy \geq 0$, $u+v \leq 0$, $x+y \leq 0$. In addition, the denominator in (1.2) is strictly positive: $-x$ and $-u$ represent the exponential rates and therefore, $x, u < 0$. Concerning the term $(uy+vx+vy)$,

$$uy+vx+vy = 0 \iff y(u+v) = -vx \iff y(u+v) = -vx = 0,$$

due to the fact that $y(u+v) \leq 0$ and $-vx \geq 0$. Next, $-vx = 0$ is equivalent to $v = 0$ (since $x < 0$). But if $v = 0$, then $y(u+v) = 0$ turns out into $uy = 0$, equivalent to $y = 0$ (since $u < 0$). In other words,

$$uy+vx+vy = 0 \iff v = y = 0,$$

which leads to a contradiction since if $v = y = 0$, then $P^* = I$ and thus $\gamma = 1$ (it is assumed that $\gamma < 1$). In consequence,

$$\rho > 0 \iff (u + v - x)(x - u + y) < 0 \text{ and } vy \neq 0, u + v \neq 0, x + y \neq 0.$$

Similarly,

$$\rho > 0 \iff (u + v - x)(x - u + y) > 0 \text{ and } vy \neq 0, u + v \neq 0, x + y \neq 0.$$

Finally, $\rho = 0$ if and only if at least one of the following conditions hold

1. $v = 0$,
2. $y = 0$,
3. $u + v = 0$,
4. $x + y = 0$,
5. $x = u + v$,
6. $u = x + y$,

where, as commented before, $v = y = 0$ leads to a contradiction.

On the other hand, the covariance function $C(\tau)$ is given by

$$C(\tau) = D_1(D - \mathbf{e})^{-1} (e^{D\tau} - 1)^2 (D - \mathbf{e})^{-1} D_1 \mathbf{e},$$

which can be expressed, for a MAP_2 in first canonical form as

$$C(\tau) = \frac{-vy(u + v - x)(x - u + y)e^{-2\tau(v+y)}(e^{\tau(v+y)} - 1)^2}{(v + y)^4}. \quad (1.3)$$

It is straightforward to check that the derivative of $C(\tau)$ is

$$C'(\tau) = \frac{-2vy(u + v - x)(x - u + y)e^{-2\tau(v+y)}(e^{\tau(v+y)} - 1)}{(v + y)^3}.$$

Then, the sign of $C(\tau)$ and $C'(\tau)$ clearly depends on the sign of $vy(u + v - x)(x - u + y)$. In addition, concerning the derivative, $e^{\tau(v+y)} > 1$ since $v + y > 0$ and $\tau > 0$. From the previous discussion about the sign of ρ , the proof is completed. \square

2 Proof of Proposition 2

The proof closely follows the previous one. Under the second canonical form, expression (1.2) turns out into

$$\gamma(\mu_2 - 2\mu_1^2) = \frac{2(u+v)^2(x+y)(x-u+y)(-x^2+ux+uy+vy)}{u^2x^2(2ux+uy+vx+vy)^2}. \quad (2.1)$$

The denominator in (2.1) is strictly positive. On one hand, $x, u < 0$ and on the other hand,

$$2ux + uy + vx + vy = u(x+y) + x(u+v) + vy, \quad (2.2)$$

where $u(x+y) \geq 0$, $x(u+v) \geq 0$, and $vy \geq 0$. Therefore, (2.2) is zero if and only if

$$u(x+y) = x(u+v) = vy = 0,$$

which leads to a contradiction since if either $v = 0$ or $y = 0$, then $xu = 0$ which is not possible. Therefore, the sign of ρ is determined by the numerator of (2.1). Specifically,

$$\rho > 0 \iff (x+y-u)(-x^2+ux+uy+vy) < 0 \text{ and } (u+v) \neq 0, (x+y) \neq 0.$$

Similarly,

$$\rho < 0 \iff (x+y-u)(-x^2+ux+uy+vy) > 0 \text{ and } (u+v) \neq 0, (x+y) \neq 0.$$

Finally, $\rho = 0$ if and only if at least one of the following conditions hold

1. $x+y-u = 0$,
2. $-x^2+ux+uy+vy = 0$,
3. $u+v = 0$,
4. $x+y = 0$.

Note that, condition 4 is incompatible with 1 and 3: if $x+y = 0$ and $x+y-u = 0$, then $u = 0$, which is impossible. In addition, if $x+y = 0$ and $u+v = 0$ can be easily seen to lead to $\gamma = 0$ and it is assumed that $\gamma < 0$ since we are considering MAP_2 s in second canonical form. In similar way, condition 3 is incompatible with 2 (and 4): if $u+v = 0$ and $-x^2+ux+uy+vy = 0$, then $x^2 = xu = 0$, which leads to a contradiction.

The covariance function for a MAP_2 in second canonical form is found to be given as

$$C(\tau) = \frac{-(u+v)(x-u+y)(-x^2+ux+uy+vy)(e^{\tau(u+v+x)} - 1)^2}{(u+v+x)^4},$$

with derivative given by

$$C'(\tau) = \frac{-2(u+v)(x-u+y)(-x^2+ux+uy+vy)(e^{\tau(u+v+x)}-1)e^{\tau(u+v+x)}}{(u+v+x)^3}.$$

Note that, in the denominators, $u+v+x \neq 0$ due to the fact that $x < 0$ and $u+v \leq 0$. Also, the sign of C and its derivative is equal since $u+v+x < 0$ and then, $e^{\tau(u+v+x)}-1 < 0$ but also $(u+v+x)^3 < 0$. Therefore, from the conditions under which $\rho > 0$, $\rho < 0$ and $\rho = 0$ and their relationships with the expressions of $C(\tau)$ and $C'(\tau)$, the proof is completed. \square

3 Proof of Proposition 3

From the definitions of $V(\tau)$ and $C(\tau)$, $R(\tau)$ can be expressed as

$$R(\tau) = \frac{\mathbf{a} (e^{D\tau} - I)^2 \mathbf{b}}{(\lambda^* - 2(\lambda^*)^2 - 2\mathbf{a}D_1\mathbf{e})\tau - 2\mathbf{a} (e^{D\tau-I}) \mathbf{b}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} &= \pi D_1 (D - \mathbf{e}\pi)^{-1}, \\ \mathbf{b} &= (D - \mathbf{e}\pi)^{-1} D_1 \mathbf{e}, \end{aligned}$$

and $D = D_0 + D_1$ is the infinitesimal generator matrix of the Markov process $J(t)$ with stationary probability vector π . Since D is the generator matrix of the continuous Markov process $J(t)$ then,

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} e^{D\tau} = \Pi,$$

where Π is a $m \times m$ matrix with all rows equal to π . Therefore, regarding the numerator of (3.1),

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{a} (e^{D\tau} - I)^2 \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a} (\Pi - I)^2 \mathbf{b},$$

a constant value and

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} (\lambda^* - 2(\lambda^*)^2 - 2\mathbf{a}D_1\mathbf{e})\tau - 2\mathbf{a} (e^{D\tau-I}) \mathbf{b} = \infty,$$

which completes the proof. \square .

4 Performance of the estimation method

This section presents a deeper analysis regarding the performance of the proposed estimation method for the MAP_2 . It considers both the synthetic and real traces described in the main manuscript.

4.1 Synthetic data sets

As commented at the end of Subsection 4.2 in the main manuscript, the novel approach for inference of the MAP_2 has been tested using the synthetic dataset defined by the rate matrices

$$D_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -0.81 & 0.04 \\ 0 & -5.88 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.76 & 0 \\ 0.09 & 5.79 \end{pmatrix}.$$

A total of 50 traces of length 100 of inter-arrival times were simulated. Problem (P) was run using as starting point the solution of the problem where $\beta_2 = 0$ (and thus, no information concerning the counting process is included in the inference process). This solution was given by

$$\hat{D}_0(0) = \begin{pmatrix} -0.90 & 0.12 \\ 0 & -11.80 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1(0) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.78 & 0 \\ 0.60 & 11.20 \end{pmatrix},$$

which, as described in Subsection 4.1 of the main manuscript, provided a reasonable approximation of the inter-arrival time distribution, but a poor performance over the counting process descriptors. In order to overcome this issue, (P) was run under three possible situations, $k = 1, 3, 5$, and using both the inter-arrival empirical moments $(\bar{\mu}_1, \bar{\mu}_2, \bar{\mu}_3, \bar{\rho}) = (0.377, 0.714, 2.352, 0.308)$ and information regarding the empirical correlation function $\bar{R}(\tau)$. In all cases, the empirical values of both the inter-arrival distribution as well as the correlation function, were almost perfectly recovered, that is the value of the objective function $\delta(\boldsymbol{\theta}, (\tau_1^*, \dots, \tau_k^*))$ as in (4.3) of the main manuscript was close to 0 taking values less than 10^{-6} .

In the first case, the counting process descriptor with $\tau_1^* = 1$ was used: $\bar{R}(1) = 0.6316$. For this case the solution was

$$\hat{D}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -0.8885 & 0.0767 \\ 0 & -10.3440 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.8118 & 0 \\ 0.3244 & 10.0195 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then, the value of k was increased up to 3, taking $\tau_1^* = 0.5, \tau_2^* = 1, \tau_3^* = 1.5$ and $(\bar{R}(0.5), \bar{R}(1), \bar{R}(1.5)) = (0.5076, 0.6316, 0.6472)$. For this situation, the solution changed to

$$\hat{D}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -0.8148 & 0.0573 \\ 0 & -6.1232 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.7575 & 0 \\ 0.1132 & 6.0100 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Finally, k was set to 5 using $\tau_1^* = 0.5, \tau_2^* = 1, \tau_3^* = 1.5, \tau_4^* = 2, \tau_5^* = 2.5$, where $(\bar{R}(0.5), \bar{R}(1), \bar{R}(1.5), \bar{R}(2), \bar{R}(2.5)) = (0.5076, 0.6316, 0.6472, 0.6815, 0.6858)$. The results in the case were

$$\hat{D}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -0.8060 & 0.0458 \\ 0 & -5.8442 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \hat{D}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.7602 & 0 \\ 0.0843 & 5.7599 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Figure 10 of the main manuscript showed the evolution of the fit to the empirical correlation function when k increases. As expected, the larger the value of k , the better

approximation of the curve. The same conclusion can be obtained by looking at the fit of other counting process descriptors, namely, the expected number of counts, the variance, and the Variance-to-Mean ratio defined by expressions (3.5), (3.6) and (2.1), of the main manuscript. Figure 1 depicts the estimation of the three quantities. It is interesting to note that the fit to $E[N(\tau)]$ does not vary pretty much among the considered scenarios: this is due to the fact that $E[N(\tau)]$ only depends on λ^* , the inverse of the first moment of the inter-arrival time distribution, μ_1 , a descriptor that is considered by (P) for all values of k (including $k = 0$).

Figure 1: Empirical mean (top left), variance (top right) and overdispersion (bottom) functions (in solid line) and fits under the new approach (dotted red, green and black lines) and under the approach based only on inter-arrival moments (dotted blue line).

4.2 Real data set

We present here the results obtained regarding the time slots G_1 and $G_3 - G_6$. Tables 1-5 show the empirical values of the expected number of arrivals, variance, correlation and index of dispersion evaluated in a grid of amplitudes τ s, and three estimators each one obtained under a different value of k in Algorithm 1 (see Subsection 4.2 of the main manuscript): under $k = 1$, the choice of the amplitude was $\tau_1^* = 0.25$. Under $k = 3$, $\tau_1^* = 0.25$, $\tau_2^* = 0.5$ and $\tau_3^* = 0.75$. Finally, $k = 5$ and $\tau_1^* = 0.25$, $\tau_2^* = 0.5$, $\tau_3^* = 0.75$,

$\tau_4^* = 1$, $\tau_5^* = 1.25$ were used. The conclusions from the tables are analogous to those commented regarding Table 3 of the main manuscript.

Table 1: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the first slot G_1 (7-9h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.1	3.989	4.168	5.477	9.795	0.181	0.118	1.373	2.350
		4.213		6.081		0.292		1.443
		4.192		5.702		0.242		1.360
0.2	8.534	8.336	12.104	21.886	0.359	0.211	1.418	2.626
		8.426		15.711		0.402		1.865
		8.383		14.165		0.361		1.690
0.3	10.386	12.504	24.038	36.265	0.468	0.285	2.314	2.900
		12.639		28.487		0.445		2.254
		12.575		25.178		0.423		2.002
0.4	17.409	16.671	32.945	52.92	0.488	0.346	1.892	3.174
		16.853		44.051		0.457		2.614
		16.766		38.545		0.455		2.299
0.5	22.159	20.839	52.020	71.842	0.500	0.396	2.348	3.447
		21.066		62.089		0.454		2.947
		20.958		54.088		0.470		2.581
0.6	20.568	25.007	50.214	93.02	0.484	0.439	2.441	3.720
		25.279		82.318		0.443		3.256
		25.149		71.638		0.475		2.849
0.7	32	29.175	68.808	116.446	0.466	0.475	2.15	3.991
		29.492		104.491		0.428		3.543
		29.341		91.043		0.473		3.103
0.8	23.727	33.343	79.087	142.108	0.359	0.5106	3.333	4.262
		33.705		128.387		0.411		3.809
		33.532		112.160		0.466		3.345
0.9	38.352	37.511	109.886	169.997	0.529	0.533	2.865	4.532
		37.918		153.810		0.392		4.056
		37.724		134.858		0.457		3.575
1	42.898	41.678	133.126	200.104	0.482	0.557	3.103	4.801
		42.132		180.588		0.374		4.286
		41.915		159.017		0.447		3.794

Table 2: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the slot G_3 (11-16h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.1	8.568	8.649	9.194	10.129	0.132	0.145	1.073	1.171
		8.630		9.943		0.127		1.152
		8.634		9.955		0.130		1.153
0.2	17.182	17.298	22.896	23.203	0.198	0.252	1.333	1.341
		17.261		22.403		0.221		1.298
		17.267		22.508		0.225		1.303
0.3	26.341	25.947	32.899	39.197	0.318	0.332	1.249	1.511
		25.891		37.339		0.294		1.442
		25.901		37.589		0.295		1.451
0.4	34.182	34.596	52.116	58.087	0.366	0.396	1.525	1.679
		34.521		54.713		0.351		1.585
		34.535		55.133		0.348		1.596
0.5	43.307	43.245	65.996	79.849	0.342	0.446	1.524	1.846
		43.152		74.484		0.397		1.726
		43.168		75.074		0.389		1.739
0.6	51.409	51.894	106.968	104.458	0.368	0.487	2.081	2.013
		51.782		96.617		0.433		1.866
		51.802		97.350		0.421		1.879
0.7	60.057	60.543	111.751	131.893	0.411	0.52	1.861	2.179
		60.412		121.072		0.463		2.004
		60.435		121.900		0.446		2.017
0.8	68.955	69.192	135.446	162.128	0.381	0.548	1.964	2.343
		69.043		147.814		0.488		2.141
		69.069		148.663		0.466		2.152
0.9	75.250	77.841	142.521	195.141	0.464	0.572	1.894	2.507
		77.673		176.806		0.508		2.276
		77.703		177.582		0.481		2.285
1	85.636	86.490	173.4	230.909	0.430	0.592	2.025	2.670
		86.303		208.013		0.525		2.410
		86.336		208.600		0.493		2.416

Table 3: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the slot G_4 (16-17h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.05	3.330	3.825	3.502	4.250	0.077	0.082	1.052	1.111
		3.721		3.991		0.067		1.072
		3.748		4.101		0.084		1.094
0.1	6.625	7.650	7.039	9.200	0.114	0.114	1.062	1.202
		7.443		8.520		0.126		1.145
		7.496		8.893		0.149		1.187
0.15	10.455	11.475	11.308	14.650	0.180	0.123	1.082	1.276
		11.164		13.588		0.178		1.217
		11.244		14.354		0.200		1.277
0.2	13.864	15.300	14.852	20.480	0.277	0.121	1.071	1.338
		14.886		19.194		0.224		1.289
		14.992		20.452		0.241		1.364
0.25	17.182	19.125	23.285	26.590	0.340	0.115	1.355	1.390
		18.607		25.340		0.265		1.362
		18.740		27.164		0.272		1.450
0.3	20.795	22.951	26.790	32.900	0.237	0.107	1.288	1.433
		22.328		32.022		0.302		1.434
		22.488		34.466		0.297		1.532
0.35	24.591	26.776	29.638	39.355	0.301	0.098	1.205	1.470
		26.050		39.242		0.336		1.506
		26.236		42.334		0.317		1.613
0.4	27.932	30.601	33.277	45.923	0.406	0.090	1.191	1.501
		29.770		47.001		0.366		1.578
		29.984		50.746		0.332		1.692
0.45	31.045	34.426	49.160	52.572	0.325	0.083	1.583	1.527
		33.493		55.297		0.394		1.651
		33.732		59.680		0.344		1.769
0.5	32.966	38.251	57.732	59.280	0.481	0.076	1.751	1.550
		37.214		64.132		0.419		1.723
		37.479		69.115		0.353		1.844

Table 4: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the slot G_5 (17-22h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.1	4.716	4.679	5.510	5.949	0.179	0.190	1.168	1.271
		4.671		5.391		0.134		1.154
		4.672		5.459		0.143		1.169
0.2	9.545	9.358	13.232	14.163	0.197	0.271	1.386	1.513
		9.342		12.222		0.235		1.308
		9.344		12.483		0.248		1.336
0.3	14.159	14.037	22.526	24.277	0.266	0.302	1.591	1.729
		14.014		20.492		0.316		1.462
		14.016		21.057		0.328		1.502
0.4	19.250	18.716	33.433	35.987	0.491	0.309	1.737	1.923
		18.685		30.200		0.381		1.616
		18.688		31.164		0.390		1.668
0.5	24.125	23.395	44.615	49.037	0.409	0.305	1.849	2.096
		23.356		41.344		0.434		1.770
		23.360		42.791		0.440		1.832
0.6	28.227	28.074	45.668	63.212	0.440	0.294	1.618	2.252
		28.027		53.925		0.479		1.924
		28.032		55.923		0.480		1.995
0.7	32.307	32.753	64.626	78.331	0.618	0.280	2.000	2.392
		32.698		67.941		0.517		2.078
		32.703		70.546		0.513		2.157
0.8	36.659	37.432	83.959	94.243	0.512	0.265	2.290	2.518
		37.370		83.391		0.550		2.232
		37.375		86.643		0.540		2.318
0.9	41.080	42.111	94.379	110.820	0.573	0.249	2.297	2.632
		42.041		100.274		0.579		2.385
		42.047		104.203		0.563		2.478
1	48.250	46.790	125.725	127.956	0.628	0.234	2.606	2.735
		46.712		118.590		0.604		2.539
		46.719		123.209		0.582		2.637

Table 5: Fit to the counting process of the real inter-arrival dataset for the slot G_6 (22-24h)

τ	$E[N(\tau)]$		$V[N(\tau)]$		$R(\tau)$		$VtM[N(\tau)]$	
	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted	empirical	fitted
0.1	3.898	3.563	4.205	5.060	0.070	0.233	1.079	1.420
		3.520		4.225		0.164		1.200
		3.525		4.433		0.195		1.258
0.2	7.739	7.127	9.753	12.477	0.244	0.270	1.260	1.751
		7.040		9.833		0.274		1.397
		7.050		10.596		0.304		1.503
0.3	12.205	10.690	14.539	21.524	0.293	0.258	1.191	2.014
		10.560		16.790		0.352		1.590
		10.575		18.369		0.369		1.737
0.4	16.591	14.253	33.782	31.699	0.339	0.232	2.036	2.224
		14.080		25.060		0.408		1.780
		14.100		27.642		0.406		1.960
0.5	19.648	17.816	35.312	42.651	0.528	0.206	1.797	2.394
		17.600		34.607		0.450		1.966
		17.625		38.310		0.428		2.174
0.6	21.795	21.380	40.217	54.143	0.464	0.181	1.845	2.532
		21.119		45.398		0.481		2.150
		21.150		50.277		0.439		2.377
0.7	27.909	24.943	60.038	66.006	0.479	0.160	2.151	2.646
		24.639		57.401		0.505		2.330
		24.675		63.453		0.444		2.572
0.8	29.864	28.506	67.469	78.127	0.482	0.142	2.259	2.741
		28.159		70.583		0.523		2.507
		28.200		77.754		0.443		2.757
0.9	34.602	32.069	91.544	90.426	0.438	0.127	2.646	2.820
		31.679		84.914		0.536		2.680
		31.725		93.103		0.439		2.935
1	35.943	35.633	107.481	102.848	0.350	0.114	2.990	2.886
		35.199		100.363		0.546		2.851
		35.249		109.428		0.433		3.104

5 Probability models for fitting service and impatience times

This section describes the probability models that have been fitted to either the service times or the impatience times in the main manuscript.

- **Log-normal distribution.** A positive random variable X is log-normally distributed with parameters $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\sigma > 0$, $X \sim \text{LN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$, if its density function is given by:

$$f_X(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma x \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad \text{for all } x > 0.$$

- **Weibull distribution.** A positive random variable X is distributed according to a Weibull distribution with shape parameter $\alpha > 0$ and scale parameter $\lambda > 0$, $X \sim \text{Weibull}(\alpha, \lambda)$, if its density function is given by:

$$f_X(x) = \lambda \alpha (\lambda x)^{\alpha-1} \exp(-\lambda x)^\alpha, \quad \text{for all } x > 0.$$

- **PH distribution.** A positive random variable X is distributed according to phase-type distribution of order n ($PH(n)$) with parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and \mathbf{T} , $X \sim PH(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{T})$ if its density function is given by:

$$f_X(x) = \boldsymbol{\alpha} e^{\mathbf{T}x} (-\mathbf{T} \mathbf{e}), \quad \text{for all } x > 0.$$

Where \mathbf{e} is a column vector of ones, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is a sub-stochastic vector of length n and \mathbf{T} is a sub-generator matrix of dimension $n \times n$.

- **Birbaum-Saunders distribution.** A positive random variable X is distributed according to a Birbaum-Saunders distribution with shape parameter $\alpha > 0$ and scale parameter $\beta > 0$, $X \sim BS(\alpha, \beta)$, if its density function is given by:

$$f_X(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \exp\left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{\beta}} - \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{x}}\right)^2}{2\alpha^2}\right) \left(\frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{\beta}} + \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{x}}\right)}{2\alpha x}\right), \quad \text{for all } x > 0.$$

6 Fit of the service and impatience time for time slots G_2, \dots, G_6

In this section Figure 2 reports the fits provided by the LN , Weibull and $PH(2)$ distributions to the service times corresponding to slots G_2, \dots, G_6 . Similar conclusions as those regarding Figure 4 of the main manuscript are obtained here: LN slightly outperforms the Weibull and the $PH(2)$ distribution is the one that performs the worst. Regarding the impatience times, we illustrate by Figure 3 the comparison between the fits provided by the BS and $PH(2)$ distributions. Note that, similarly as shown in the main manuscript, the BS distribution clearly outperforms the $PH(2)$.

7 Sensitivity analysis regarding the inter-arrival times correlation

The purpose of this section is to analyze the effect over the queueing system of the inter-arrival times first-lag autocorrelation coefficient. This quantity, represented by $\rho_1 = \rho_T(1)$, is defined in Eq. (3.4) in the main manuscript. The numerical experiment has been designed as follows. Since the MAP_2 is characterized by four inter-arrival descriptors, ρ_1 and μ_1, μ_2, μ_3 , as in Eq. (3.3) in the main manuscript, then three different MAP_2 representations $\{D_0, D_1\}$ have been considered with equal values for μ_1, μ_2 and μ_3 , and three different values of ρ_1 . Specifically, $\mu_1 = 0.66, \mu_2 = 1.77, \mu_3 = 7.33$, and $\rho_1 \in \{-0.26, 0, 0.25\}$. Once the arrival processes are defined, then a LN service distribution (with parameters $\mu = 0.5$ and $\sigma = 1$), impatience times distributed as a BS distribution (with parameters $\alpha = 1.66$ and scale $\beta = 8.39$) are set. Finally, two different values of the number of servers have been tested, $C \in \{5, 10\}$. The simulator of the queue $MAP_2/LN/C$ described in Subsection 5.2 of the main manuscript has been used to sample the behavior of $n = 1000$ customers. Table 6 depicts the estimated steady-state queue length distribution, where the probabilities have been obtained by averaging over 50 replications of the simulator of the queue. On the other hand, Figure 4 illustrates the estimated virtual waiting time distribution for the three considered values of ρ_1 , and for the two choices of the number of servers: $C = 5$ (left panel) and $C = 10$ (right panel).

Figure 2: Fit of the service times by the LN , Weibull and $PH(2)$ distributions for the time slots G_2 (top left), G_3 (top right), G_4 (central left), G_5 (central right) and G_6 (bottom left).

Figure 3: Fit of the impatience times by the LN and $PH(2)$ distributions for the time slots G_2 (top left), G_3 (top right), G_4 (central left), G_5 (central right) and G_6 (bottom left).

	ρ_1	π_0	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4	$\sum_{j=5}^{\infty} \pi_j$	<i>Abandon rates</i>
$C = 5$	-0.26	0.808	0.086	0.048	0.028	0.014	0.016	19.27%
	0	0.774	0.077	0.052	0.034	0.022	0.041	23.21%
	0.25	0.754	0.043	0.034	0.028	0.024	0.118	29.73%
$C = 10$	-0.26	0.990	0.006	0.003	0.001	3.08E-04	2.17E-04	1.60%
	0	0.975	0.012	0.006	0.003	0.002	1.62E-03	3.92%
	0.25	0.934	0.013	0.010	0.008	0.007	0.029	13.85%

Table 6: Steady-state queue length distributions under different inter-arrival times first-lag autocorrelation coefficient (ρ_1).

Figure 4: Virtual waiting time distribution for $C = 5$ (left) and $C = 10$ (right) under different inter-arrival times first-lag autocorrelation coefficient (ρ_1).

The previous results show that the value of ρ_1 seems to have an impact over both the queue length and virtual time distributions. First, the abandon rates increase with the value of ρ_1 , for the two considered situations regarding the number of servers. The same occurs with the probability of having 5 or more customers in the queue. On the contrary, the probability of having 0 clients in the queue decrease with ρ_1 . On the other hand, as ρ_1 increases, the converge of the virtual time distribution to 1 slows down. The described behaviors have been observed for other values of the inter-arrival time moments

(μ_i) and different values of the service times (μ, σ) and impatience times distributions (α, β) . The theoretical proof for such results is out of the scope of this paper and shall will be addressed in future works.